

Synthesis in 3-Azafluorene Group. Part-III

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The Hey-Elks route to arylated pyridines has been utilised in the synthesis of 3-azafluorenes. The pyrido-coumarin (23) and the related chromene (24) have been synthesised.

SINCE the first synthesis of 3-azafluorene and its derivatives^{1,2} from this laboratory, a number of papers³⁻⁵ have appeared describing researches in this area. The development involved synthesis from appropriate pyridine derivatives. The pyrido-coumarin (23) was not known and as its facile transformation into the related chromenes could be predicted, a better route to 3-azafluorene group was sought. It transpired that a short synthesis of 3-aryl-4-methylpyridines may be effected by using free-radical substitution in pyridine system following classical researches of Hey *et al.*⁶ and a successful outcome of this approach is described herein.

Free aryl radicals could be generated by the decomposition of relevant triazens. Thus, 1-(2'-naphthyl)-3,3'-dimethyltriazene (1) on reaction with 4-picoline at 100° in presence of hydrogen chloride gave a mixture of 3- and 2-(2'-naphthyl)-4-methylpyridine (6 and 11) in the ratio of 2:3. Their separation was conveniently effected by fractional crystallisation of the picrates^{6,7}. The triazene (2) on similar reaction with 4-picoline afforded only one product (12).

and *peri*-hydrogen atom when the 1'-naphthyl radical attacks the 3-position. In the preparation of 10, the presence of the isomer 15 could not be detected. Here too, the *ortho*-methoxyl group of the attacking radical was responsible for the formation of the product. Excepting these, all other triazens (3-4) have produced pairs of isomers (8-14). In all of these cases, 2-aryl-4-picolines are formed in greater amount for steric reasons.

The oxidation of aryl-4-picolines by potassium permanganate could not be successfully carried out. Use of selenium dioxide in xylene under the conditions laid down by Marcot and Pollard⁸ also proved abortive even when the reaction was carried out under forcing conditions. Success was eventually obtained by employing the same reagent using the recipe of Jackson *et al.*⁹ with a slight modification when 54-67% of the acids (16-19) were obtained. Similarly, the 2-arylated pyridines (11-15) were smoothly oxidised. Some of these acids were decarboxylated (using copper-bronze) and the corresponding aryl pyridines isolated which were characterised (see experimental).

The acid chloride derived from 16 was smoothly cyclised by aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene to give the azafluorenone (20) as an orange solid. Similarly, 21 and 22 were obtained; these were not accompanied by isomeric products. Each of the azafluorenones was derivatised and their uv and ir spectra studied.

The formation of a single isomer may be explained by the strong steric repulsion of the methyl group

3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid on demethylation (hydrobromic acid/acetic acid) gave a quantitative yield of the coumarin (23) $\nu_{\max}$ 1725 cm^{-1} (CO). When treated with phenylmagnesium bromide 23 gave the diphenylchromene derivative (24).

The structure is supported by ir spectrum (absence of C=O) and by mass spectrum which showed M^+ 335 with a base peak at m/z 258 which undoubtedly corresponds to the pyrylium ion (25).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 and 577 spectrophotometer.

1-(2'-Naphthyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (1): A suspension of 2-naphthylamine (5.0 g) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml) was cooled and treated with cold aqueous sodium nitrite solution (2.6 g in 6.5 ml) dropwise and the temperature maintained below 4°. The resulting 2-naphthyl diazonium chloride solution was added dropwise to a mixture of dimethylamine solution (14 ml, 40%) and sodium carbonate solution (150 ml, 30%) in water with stirring during 2 h. A dark red solid separated which was filtered, dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) as shining colourless needles, m.p. 58° (lit.⁶ 57-58°). The other substituted triazens were also prepared in the similar manner. 1-(1'-Naphthyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (2) was obtained as a viscous reddish oil, b.p. 120°/0.8 mm (lit.^{10,11} 127°/0.6 mm, m.p. 41°); 1-(*m*-tolyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (3) as a liquid, b.p. 122°/22 mm (lit.¹¹ 79°/35 mm); 1-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (4) as a liquid, b.p. 139°/7 mm (lit.¹¹ 105°/0.6 mm); 1-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (5) as a liquid, b.p. 159-160°/15 mm (lit.¹² 123-24°/8 mm).

3-(2'-Naphthyl)-4-methylpyridine (6) and 2-(2'-naphthyl)-4-methylpyridine (11): 1-(2'-Naphthyl)-3,3-dimethyltriazen (4.0 g) was dissolved in dry 4-picoline (40 ml). The reaction mixture was saturated with hydrogen chloride at 100°. The solidified mass was left overnight at room temperature. The solid mass was made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution (50%). The mixture was extracted with benzene and evaporation of the dried extract (KOH) gave an oil which was distilled at 160-185°/0.6 mm. Tlc showed two distinct spots corresponding to 6 and 11. For the separation of these a saturated solution of picric acid (1.6 g) in alcohol was added to the alcoholic solution of the mixture. The mixture was boiled, left for crystallisation. The mixture of picrates was filtered and on repeated fractional crystallisation furnished two picrates (i) picrate of 6, m.p. 182° (Found: C, 58.59; H, 4.39. $C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$ requires C, 58.93; H, 3.60%), (ii) picrate of 11, m.p. 212° (Found: C, 58.49; H, 3.89. $C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$ requires C, 58.92; H, 3.60%). The picrate of 6 was mixed with concentrated ammonia (50 ml) and the mixture was left overnight. The reaction mixture was heated for 10 min on a water bath and then cooled. On extraction with benzene and evaporation of the dried extract (KOH) a liquid was obtained which distilled at 165°/0.6 mm to furnish 6 (Found: C, 87.30; H, 6.45. $C_{16}H_{12}N$ requires C, 87.64; H, 5.98%). Similarly, the picrate of 11 yielded 11 as a viscous oil which solidified on keeping. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colourless prisms (0.52 g), m.p. 59-60° (Found: C, 87.25; H, 6.3. $C_{16}H_{12}N$ requires C, 87.64; H, 5.98%). Similarly, 7-11 and 12-15 were separated by way of their picrates (Table I).

3-(2'-Naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (16): A mixture of 3-(2'-naphthyl)-4-methylpyridine (0.5 g, 1 mol) and selenium dioxide (0.5 g, 2 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was heated at 105° under anhydrous condition for 10 h and then left at room temperature. The separated selenium was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to remove pyridine. The residue was dissolved in saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate on acidification (HCl) yielded 3-(2'-naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic

TABLE I

Compd no.	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd).		M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Picrate		
			O	H			O	H	N
12	98	$C_{16}H_{12}N$	87.20 (87.64)	6.20 (5.98)	221	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$	58.72 (58.93)	4.80 (4.39)	12.20 (12.60)
8	50	$C_{16}H_{12}N$	84.91 (85.20)	7.31 (7.15)	152	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4O_7$	55.23 (55.84)	4.18 (3.91)	13.38 (13.59)
13	77	$C_{16}H_{12}N$	84.98 (85.20)	7.27 (7.15)	182	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$	55.10 (55.84)	4.20 (3.91)	13.26 (13.59)
9	Yellow oil	$C_{16}H_{12}NO$	78.15 (78.36)	6.61 (6.58)	140	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$	52.75 (53.27)	3.88 (3.77)	12.67 (13.08)
14	Yellow oil	$C_{16}H_{12}NO$	78.20 (78.36)	6.59 (6.58)	165	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$	52.95 (53.27)	3.98 (3.77)	12.85 (13.08)
10	Yellow oil	$C_{16}H_{12}NO$	78.18 (78.36)	6.41 (6.58)	189	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_7$	52.95 (53.27)	3.05 (3.77)	13.08 (13.68)

acid (3.38 g) (16). It was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 284-85° (Found: C, 76.82; H, 4.67. $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 77.09; H, 4.45%), ν_{max} 1715 cm^{-1} (COOH). Similarly prepared, 3-(*m*-tolyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (17) was obtained as shining colourless crystals, m.p. 232° (Found: C, 73.16; H, 5.35. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 73.22; H, 5.20%), ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (COOH); 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (18) as colourless shining crystals, m.p. 180° (Found: C, 67.85; H, 5.1. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 68.11; H, 4.85%), ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (COOH); 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (19) in prisms, m.p. 238° (Found: C, 67.82; H, 5.20. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 68.11; H, 4.85%), ν_{max} 1700 cm^{-1} (COOH).

By adopting a similar procedure 2-(2'-naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid was obtained as needles, m.p. 287° (Found: C, 76.79; H, 4.50. $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 77.09; H, 4.45%), ν_{max} 1715 cm^{-1} (COOH); 2-(1'-naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 256° (Found: C, 77.0; H, 4.50. $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 77.09; H, 4.45%), ν_{max} 1715 cm^{-1} (COOH); 2-(*m*-tolyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid as shining colourless crystals, m.p. 241° (Found: C, 73.10; H, 5.29. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 73.22; H, 5.20%), ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (COOH); 2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid as colourless crystals, m.p. 203° (Found: C, 67.80; H, 5.20. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 68.11; H, 4.85%), ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (COOH).

3-(2'-Naphthyl)pyridine: A mixture of 3-(2'-naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (0.04 g) and copper-bronze (0.06 g) was heated gently till the evolution of gas ceased. The mass was extracted with benzene and chromatographed over alumina. 3-(2'-Naphthyl)pyridine was obtained as crystals, m.p. 101° (lit.¹³ 102-103°). The picrate was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 202° (lit.¹³ 200°). Similarly prepared, 3-(*m*-tolyl)pyridine was obtained as a yellow oil, the picrate separated as yellow prisms, m.p. 187° (Found: C, 84.96; H, 6.65. $C_{15}H_{11}N$ requires C, 85.17; H, 6.55%); 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine as yellow oil, the picrate separated as yellow needles, m.p. 180° (lit.¹⁴ 182°).

By applying the same procedure 2-(2'-naphthyl)pyridine was obtained as colourless crystals, m.p. 72° (lit.¹⁵ 71-72°), the picrate separated as yellow needles, m.p. 178-180° (lit.¹⁵ 175-175.5°); 2-(1'-naphthyl)pyridine as yellow oil, the picrate separated as yellow needles, m.p. 197° (lit.^{16,17} 199.5°); 2-(*m*-tolyl)pyridine as yellow oil, the picrate separated as yellow prisms, m.p. 183° (lit.¹⁸ 183.5°); 2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine as yellow oil, the picrate as yellow needles, m.p. 154° (lit.¹⁹ 154-155°).

7,8-Benzo-3-azafluorenone (20): The acid chloride prepared from 3-(2'-naphthyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (16) (0.2 g) was dissolved in dry nitrobenzene and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.3 g) was added with occasional shaking. The colour changed to orange red. The reaction mixture was

left overnight at room temperature and steam distilled. 7,8-Benzo-3-azafluorenone (20) was separated as orange-red solid which crystallised from benzene in orange-red small needles (0.13 g, 70%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 82.88; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_9NO$ requires C, 83.10; H, 3.92%), ν_{max} 1700 cm^{-1} (CO); λ_{max} 246, 292, 385 nm, $\log \epsilon$ 4.54, 4.32, 3.66. Similarly, 6-methyl-3-azafluorenone (21) separated as yellow shining crystals (76%), m.p. 105° (Found: C, 79.88; H, 4.78. $C_{15}H_9NO$ requires C, 79.98; H, 4.65%), ν_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} (CO); λ_{max} 258, 328 nm; $\log \epsilon$ 4.44, 3.54; 6-methoxy-3-azafluorenone (22) as yellow shining crystals (73%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 73.80; H, 4.51. $C_{15}H_9NO_2$ requires C, 73.92; H, 4.30%), ν_{max} 1700 cm^{-1} (CO); λ_{max} 277, 245 nm; $\log \epsilon$ 4.32, 3.70.

Pyrido[4,3-*c*] coumarin (23): A mixture of 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)pyridine-4-carboxylic acid (19) (0.2 g) and hydrobromic acid (0.3 ml, 48%) in glacial acetic acid (6 ml) was refluxed at 130° for 6 h. Acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure and diluted with water. Pyrido[4,3-*c*]coumarin which separated was crystallised from benzene in needles (0.7 g), m.p. 186°. The compound was insoluble in cold sodium bicarbonate solution (Found: C, 73.0; H, 4.1. $C_{15}H_7NO_2$ requires C, 73.09; H, 3.85%), ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone ring). The picrate separated in yellow needles, m.p. 230° (Found: C, 50.61; H, 2.47. $C_{15}H_{10}N_4O_6$ requires C, 50.70; H, 2.35%).

2,2-Diphenylbenzo[*b*]pyrido[4,3-*d*]-1,2-pyran (24): Pyrido[4,3-*c*]coumarin (0.05 g, 1.0 mol) in dry benzene was added to the ethereal solution of phenylmagnesium bromide (0.116 g, 2.5 mol) (prepared from magnesium 0.016 g and bromobenzene 0.1 g). The mixture was refluxed for 4 h and left overnight. On working up in the usual manner 2,2-diphenylbenzo[*b*]pyrido[4,3-*d*]-1,2-pyran (24) separated as white crystals which were crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as shining needles, m.p. 198° (Found: C, 85.83; H, 5.30. $C_{20}H_{17}NO$ requires C, 85.94; H, 5.11%); M^+ (*m/z*) 335 (base peak 258).

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